

Epstein-Barr virus induced gene 2 or G protein-coupled receptor 183 (GPR183 / EBI2): Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : EBI2 is a protein encoded by the GPR183 gene and was identified due to its upregulation during Epstein-Barr virus infection of the Burkitt's lymphoma cell line BL41. GPR183 has been implicated in HIV/SIV, chronic rhinosinusitis, positioning and homeostasis of dendritic cells in the spleen, in bone surfaces, multiple sclerosis, human malaria, diabetes, neuropathic pain, mycobacterium tuberculosis, inflammatory bowel disease, activation of brown adipose tissue, influenza A virus (IAV) and severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) infection. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of GPR183, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited

*ML dicoveries of GPR183 synergy in Meningiomas

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grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: GPR183, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplas-

tic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagioccephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. EpsteinBarr virus (EBV) or human herpesvirus 4 (HHV-4)

Orthoherpesviridae or Herpesviridae, is a large family of DNA viruses that cause infections and certain diseases in animals, including humans. Beswick [13] clarified the terminology of the word herpes. Via DNA polymerase, a DNA virus has a genome made of deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) that is replicated. They are classified as those

- having two strands of DNA in their genome, called double-stranded DNA (dsDNA) viruses, and those
- having one strand of DNA in their genome, called single-stranded DNA (ssDNA) viruses.

Of the 9 known human herpesviridae (or herpesvirus) types in the herpes family, the EpsteinBarr virus (EBV), also known as human herpesvirus 4 (HHV-4), is one of the most common viruses in humans.

1.3. Thyroid hormone receptor β (GPR183)

G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs), also known as 7-(pass)-transmembrane domain receptors (7TM receptors) or heptahelical receptors or serpentine receptors or G protein-linked receptors (GPLR), form a large group of cell surface receptors. They are coupled with guanine nucleotide-binding (G) proteins. Their activity is controlled to bind to and hydrolyze guanosine triphosphate (GTP) to guanosine diphosphate (GDP). When bound to GTP, they are termed 'on', and, when bound to GDP, they are termed 'off'. G proteins belong to the larger group of enzymes called GTPases. GPCRs pass through the cell membrane seven times in the form of six loops (3 extracellular loops interacting with ligand molecules, 3 intracellular loops interacting with G proteins, an N-terminal extracellular region and a C-terminal intracellular region) of amino acid residues. Ligands can bind either to the extracellular N-terminus and loops or to the binding site within transmembrane helices. Trzaskowski et al. [14] elucidate theoretical and experimental studies to understand the action of molecular switches in GPCRs.

G-protein coupled receptor 183 also known as Epstein-Barr virus-induced G-protein coupled receptor 2 (EBI2) is a GPCR expressed on the surface of some immune cells (i.e B cells and T cells). GPR183 gene encodes the protein in humans.

Birkenbach et al. [15] cloned and identified mRNAs induced in Burkitt's lymphoma (BL) cells, since EBV infection of Burkitt's lymphoma (BL) cells in vitro reproduced many of the activation effects of EBV infection of primary B lymphocytes. They found 9 genes that encode RNAs which were 4- to > 100-fold more abundant after EBV infection, two of which CD21 and vimentin, were previously known to be induced by EBV infection, five others, i.e cathepsin H, annexin VI (p68), serglycin proteoglycan core protein, CD44, and the myristylated alanine-rich protein kinase C substrate (MARCKS), were not previously known to be induced by EBV infection and finally two novel genes, EBV-induced genes i.e EBI-1/2 could be predicted from their cDNA sequences to encode GPCR. They hypothesized that these predicted GPCRs were more likely to be mediators of EBV effects on B lymphocytes or of normal lymphocyte functions than were genes previously known to be up-regulated by EBV infection.

1.4. Roles of GPR183 in different disease

The Gastrointestinal (GI) tract is critical to AIDS pathogenesis as it is the primary site for viral transmission and a major site of viral replication and CD4⁺ T cell destruction. Consequently GI disease, a major complication of HIV/SIV infection can facilitate translocation of luminal bacterial products causing localized/systemic immune activation leading to AIDS progression. Mohan et al. [16] analyzed global gene expression profiles sequentially in the intestine of the same animals prior to and at 21 and 90d post

SIV infection (PI) and reported data w.r.t lamina propria leukocytes (LPL). Apart from a range of observations for other involved genes, they found reduced expression of GPR183 (B-cells) at 90d PI, which suggested further deterioration of overall immune function and provided significant new details on the molecular pathology of HIV/SIV induced GI disease.

Hulse et al. [17] sought to thoroughly characterize B lineage cells within sinus tissues of patients with **chronic rhinosinusitis** (CRS) and healthy control subjects and to determine whether levels of EBI2, were increased in patients with CRS. They found that nasal polyps (NPs) from patients with CRS had increased levels of both B cells and plasma cells compared with uncinate tissue from healthy control subjects. Further, they observed increased levels of EBI2 in NPs and they were positively correlated with expression of plasma cell markers (CD138 and B lymphocyte-induced maturation protein) in sinus tissue.

Spleen-resident dendritic cell (DC) populations hold positions for the capture and presentation of blood-borne antigens. Gatto et al. [18] found a difference in expression of the chemotactic receptor EBI2 (GPR183) on splenic DC subsets and that EBI2 regulated the positioning and homeostasis of DCs in the spleen. Based on observations they concluded that regulated expression of EBI2 on DC populations was critical for the generation and correct positioning of splenic DCs and the initiation of immune responses.

Bone surfaces attract hematopoietic and nonhematopoietic cells, such as osteoclasts (OCs) and osteoblasts (OBs), and are targeted by bone metastatic cancers. Nevius et al. [19] showed that the EBI2 was expressed in mouse monocyte/OC precursors (OCPs) and its oxysterol ligand $7\alpha,25$ -dihydroxycholesterol ($7\alpha,25$ -OHC) is secreted abundantly by OBs. Further, they showed that EBI2 enhances the development of large OCs by promoting OCP motility, while observing that EBI2 was also necessary and sufficient for guiding OCPs toward bone surfaces. They also observed that OCPs also secreted $7\alpha,25$ -OHC, which promoted EBI2 signaling and reduced OCP migration toward bone surfaces in vivo.

The interaction between oxysterols and EBI2 fine-tunes immune cell migration, a mechanism efficiently targeted to treat **multiple sclerosis** (MS), with say natalizumab. In previous experiments, it was shown that memory $CD4^+$ T lymphocytes migrated specifically in response to $7\alpha,25$ -OHC via EBI2 in the MS murine model experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis. Next, Clottu et al. [20] observed that EBI2 was functionally expressed on memory $CD4^+$ T cells and was enhanced under natalizumab treatment.

The RTS,S/AS01 vaccine provides partial protection against Plasmodium falciparum infection. Previously, anti-circumsporozoite protein (CSP) antibody titers and blood RNA signatures were associated with RTS,S/AS01 efficacy against controlled **human malaria** infection (CHMI). Du et al. [21] demonstrated that the transcript ratio MX2/GPR183, discriminated protected from non-protected individuals, by analyzing host blood transcriptomes from 5 RTS,S vaccination CHMI studies.

Taneera et al. [22] observed that GPR183 showed higher expression in **diabetic** compared to non-diabetic human islets with its expression co-localization with β -cells while its lack in α -cells in human islets. Further, they found that GPR183 agonist (7α -25-DHC) increased insulin secretion and protected against glucotoxicity-induced β -

cell damage in human islets. Also, silencing of GPR183 in INS-1 cells decreased the expression of proinsulin genes, and impaired insulin secretion with a concomitant decrease in cAMP generation.

Neuropathic pain is a health concern for which novel non-narcotic therapeutic targets are desperately needed. Using unbiased transcriptomic screening of the dorsal horn spinal cord after nerve injury, Braden et al. [23] identified that GPR183 is upregulated after chronic constriction injury (CCI) in rats. Their in vivo intrathecal injections of antagonists during peak pain, after CCI surgery reversed allodynia in male/female mice. In a first, they revealed a role for GPR183 in neuropathic pain.

Little is known about the role of these oxysterols during mycobacterial infections and Bartlett et al. [24] found that expression of the oxysterol-receptor GPR183 was reduced in blood from patients with tuberculosis (TB) and type 2 diabetes (T2D) compared to TB patients without T2D and was associated with TB disease severity on chest x-ray. They found that the activation of GPR183 by $7\alpha,25$ -OHC reduced growth of **mycobacterium tuberculosis** (Mtb) and *Mycobacterium bovis* BCG in primary human monocytes. Further, they found that mice lacking GPR183 had significantly increased lung Mtb burden and dysregulated IFNs during early infection.

Misselwitz et al. [25] concluded with genetic, translational and experimental studies, that oxysterol receptor GPR183 and its ligands, dihydroxylated oxysterols are implicated in **inflammatory bowel disease** (IBD) pathogenesis.

Pharmacological activation of **brown adipose tissue** (BAT) is an attractive approach for increasing energy expenditure to counteract obesity. As GPCRs are one of the major targets of clinically used drugs, Copperi et al. [26] identified GPR183, as the most highly expressed inhibitory GPCR in BAT among the examined pool of receptors. They found that activation of EBI2 using its endogenous ligand $7\alpha,25$ -dihydroxycholesterol decreased BAT-mediated energy expenditure in mice, while, mice deficient for EBI2 showed increased energy dissipation in response to cold. Their data identified the $7\alpha,25$ -dihydroxycholesterol/EBI2 signaling pathway as an unknown BAT inhibitor.

Severe viral respiratory infections are often characterised by extensive myeloid cell infiltration and activation and persistent lung tissue injury. Foo et al. [27] identified oxidised cholesterol and the oxysterol-sensing receptor GPR183 as drivers of monocyte/macrophage infiltration to the lung during **influenza A virus (IAV)** and **severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2)** infection. Their analysis of data on bronchoalveolar lavage samples from healthy controls and COVID-19 patients with moderate and severe disease revealed that CH25H, CYP7B1 and GPR183 were significantly upregulated in macrophages during COVID-19.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.5. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries.

Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.6. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [28] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [29] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [29].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning

approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [30]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [31], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [28] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [28]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [32], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") •

use `source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R")`.

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. GPR183 related synergies

Note - GPR183 was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2nd order combinations of GPR183 were recorded.

3.1.1. GPR183 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with GPR183 showed high rankings - CD38 molecule (CD38), CD74 molecule (CD74), RUNX family transcription factor 3 (RUNX3), amyloid beta precursor protein binding family A member 2 (APBA2), collagen type IX alpha 2 chain (COL9A2), protein disulfide isomerase family A member 5 (PDIA5), FRY microtubule binding protein (FRY), integrin subunit beta 5 (ITGB5), matrix metalloproteinase 2 (MMP2), procollagen C-endopeptidase enhancer (PCOLCE), unc-5 netrin receptor B (UNC5B), peripheral myelin protein 22 (PMP22), tripartite motif containing 2 (TRIM2), tetraspanin 11 (TSPAN11), vanin 1 (VNN1), par-3 family cell polarity regulator beta (PARD3B), Wnt ligand secretion mediator (WLS), chromosome 1 open reading frame 198 (C1orf198), plexin domain containing 2 (PLXDC2), PHD finger protein 24 (PHF24), plasminogen activator, urokinase (PLAU), FCH and mu domain containing endocytic adaptor 1 (FCHO1), protein tyrosine phosphatase non-receptor type 22 (PTPN22), lymphocyte cytosolic protein 1 (LCP1), tensin 3 (TNS3), interleukin 11 receptor subunit alpha (IL11RA), insulin like growth factor binding protein 4 (IGFBP4), chromosome 1 open reading frame 162 (C1orf162), tripartite motif containing 7 (TRIM7), AT-rich interaction domain 5B (ARID5B), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 4 (KCNE4), dimethylarginine dimethylaminohydrolase 1 (DDAH1), sushi domain containing 3 (SUSD3), RUNX family transcription factor 1 (RUNX1), trichohyalin (TCHH), matrix remodeling associated 8 (MXRA8), NLR family pyrin domain containing 3 (NLRP3), transmembrane protein 71 (TMEM71), trans-golgi network vesicle protein 23 homolog A (TVP23A), nephronectin (NPNT), atonal bHLH transcription factor 8 (ATOH8), integrin subunit alpha M (ITGAM), G protein-coupled receptor 27 (GPR27), microtubule associated protein 6 (MAP6), secretogranin II (SCG2), StAR related lipid transfer domain containing 5 (STARD5), interleukin 17D (IL17D), sushi domain containing 5 (SUSD5), homeobox B2 (HOXB2), CD248 molecule (CD248), dynein axonemal heavy chain 12 (DNAH12), purinergic receptor P2Y14 (P2RY14), yippee like 2 (YPEL2), family with sequence similarity 131 member A (FAM131A), calcium binding protein 4 (CABP4), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 3A1 (SLCO3A1), BCL2 family apoptosis regulator BOK (BOK), MEF2 activating motif and SAP domain containing transcriptional regulator (MAMSTR), myozenin 1 (MYOZ1), phosphodiesterase 4D interacting protein (PDE4DIP), cysteine and serine rich nuclear protein 3 (CSRNP3), class II major histocompatibility complex transactivator (CIITA), serine rich and transmembrane domain containing 1 (SERTM1), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 1 (KCNE1), NME/NM23 family member

9 (NME9), PLAG1 zinc finger (PLAG1), biglycan (BGN), EPH receptor B3 (EPHB3), phospholipase C beta 1 (PLCB1), neurotrimin (NTM), regulator of G protein signaling 6 (RGS6), pappalysin 1 (PAPPA), pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase 1 (PYCR1), nebulin (NEB), family with sequence similarity 43 member B (FAM43B), transmembrane protein 119 (TMEM119), olfactomedin like 1 (OLFML1), dual specificity phosphatase 5 pseudogene 1 (DUSP5P1), adrenoceptor alpha 2C (ADRA2C), protein kinase D1 (PRKD1), colony stimulating factor 1 (CSF1), fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2 (FLRT2), protein kinase cGMP-dependent 1 (PRKG1), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily Z member 1 (CYP4Z1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily X member 1 (CYP4X1), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A5, pseudogene (ANKRD20A5P), A-kinase anchoring protein 19 (C2orf88 / AKAP19), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 8 (ENTPD8), placenta associated 9 (PLAC9), nuclear GT-Pase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), family with sequence similarity 180 member A (FAM180A), serine/threonine kinase 31 (STK31), membrane metalloendopeptidase (MME), family with sequence similarity 180 member B (FAM180B), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 3 (DACT3), adenosine deaminase RNA specific B1 (ADARB1), sialophorin (SPN), C-type lectin domain containing 9A (CLEC9A), DLG associated protein 2 (DLGAP2), metallothionein 1F (MT1F), integrin subunit beta like 1 (ITGBL1), matrix metallopeptidase 17 (MMP17), delta like canonical Notch ligand 1 (DLL1), zinc finger protein 521 (ZNF521), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYR3), RNA, U6 small nuclear 529, pseudogene (RNU6-529P), ras homolog family member T1 pseudogene 2 (RHOT1P2), phospholipid phosphatase 4 (PLPP4), synaptotagmin 15 (SYT15), family with sequence similarity 155 member A (FAM155A / NALF1), transmembrane protein 240 (TMEM240), vitrin (VIT), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A9, pseudogene (ANKRD20A9P), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), high mobility group box 3 pseudogene 7 (HMGB3P7), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A11, pseudogene (ANKRD20A11P), teneurin transmembrane protein 3 (TENM3), RFPL1 antisense RNA 1 (RFPL1S), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 937 (LINC00937), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1907 (LINC01907), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1), LMCD1 antisense RNA 1 (LMCD1-AS1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily F member 29, pseudogene (CYP4F29P), zinc finger protein 883 (ZNF883) and sorting nexin 18 pseudogene 13 (SNX18P13).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2^{nd} order combination of GPR183 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t GPR183 with GPR183 — > CD38 / CD74 / RUNX3 / APBA2 / COL9A2 / PDIA5 / FRY / ITGB5 / MMP2 / PCOLCE / UNC5B / PMP22 / TRIM2 / TSPAN11 / VNN1 / PARD3B / WLS / C1orf198 / PLXDC2 / PHF24 / PLAU / FCHO1 / PTPN22 / LCP1 / TNS3 / IL11RA / IGFBP4 / C1orf162 / TRIM7 / ARID5B / KCNE4 / DDAH1 / SUSD3 / RUNX1 / TCHH / MXRA8 / NLRP3 / TMEM71 / TVP23A / NPNT / ATOH8 / ITGAM / GPR27 / MAP6 / SCG2 / STARD5

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS GPR183

RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T GPR183									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CD38 - GPR183	326	320	293	29	CD74 - GPR183	284	218	238	40
RUNX3 - GPR183	201	233	204	116	APBA2 - GPR183	317	238	320	4
COL9A2 - GPR183	207	205	228	128	PDIA5 - GPR183	334	230	103	378
FRY - GPR183	199	274	210	379	ITGB5 - GPR183	333	295	279	21
MMP2 - GPR183	266	232	254	106	PCOLCE - GPR183	300	277	316	32
UNC5B - GPR183	269	253	302	84	PMP22 - GPR183	241	222	280	49
TRIM2 - GPR183	222	296	264	46	TSPAN11 - GPR183	213	241	235	133
VNN1 - GPR183	256	252	256	45	PAR3B - GPR183	281	244	297	41
WLS - GPR183	273	279	218	12	C1orf198 - GPR183	238	298	252	27
PLXDC2 - GPR183	322	250	261	26	PHF24 - GPR183	212	237	233	97
PLAU - GPR183	239	235	237	91	FCHO1 - GPR183	245	208	334	68
PTPN22 - GPR183	271	254	274	129	LCPI - GPR183	303	284	335	392
TNS3 - GPR183	173	225	236	255	IL11RA - GPR183	215	224	270	83
IGFBP4 - GPR183	291	204	247	23	C1orf162 - GPR183	285	200	298	25
TRIM7 - GPR183	210	228	221	159	ARID5B - GPR183	305	248	249	9
KCNE4 - GPR183	307	239	263	86	DDAH1 - GPR183	206	287	286	18
SUSD3 - GPR183	294	236	269	11	RUNX1 - GPR183	332	249	242	33
TCHH - GPR183	290	227	305	43	MXRA8 - GPR183	287	267	175	362
NLRP3 - GPR183	265	285	319	19	TMEM71 - GPR183	255	297	289	28
TVP23A - GPR183	237	213	273	61	NPNT - GPR183	274	142	227	390
ATOH8 - GPR183	259	300	225	3	ITGAM - GPR183	267	328	307	89
GPR27 - GPR183	342	304	326	153	MAP6 - GPR183	335	301	310	202
SCG2 - GPR183	386	390	387	342	STARD5 - GPR183	306	346	341	264
IL17D - GPR183	240	349	216	141	SUSD5 - GPR183	298	381	336	160
HOXB2 - GPR183	350	340	375	230	CD248 - GPR183	295	352	373	343
DNAH12 - GPR183	297	379	378	247	P2RY14 - GPR183	325	355	352	186
YPEL2 - GPR183	246	317	232	10	FAM131A - GPR183	357	345	231	107
CABP4 - GPR183	283	332	265	100	SLCO3A1 - GPR183	318	357	357	265
BOK - GPR183	361	305	314	266	MAMSTR - GPR183	275	348	345	138
MYOZ1 - GPR183	340	336	346	267	PDE4DIP - GPR183	360	262	303	59
CSRNP3 - GPR183	328	343	260	65	CIITA - GPR183	226	353	340	101
SERTM1 - GPR183	380	376	391	268	KCNE1 - GPR183	327	338	226	161

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between GPR183 VS Individual members.

/ IL17D / SUSD5 / HOXB2 / CD248 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / YPEL2 / FAM131A / CABP4 / SLCO3A1 / BOK / MAMSTR / MYOZ1 / PDE4DIP / CSRNP3 / CIITA / SERTM1 / KCNE1 / NME9 / PLAG1 / BGN / EPHB3 / PLCB1 / NTM / RGS6 / PAPP / PYCR1 / NEB / FAM43B / TMEM119 / OLFML1 / DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C / PRKD1 / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / SHC4 / CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 / ANKRD20A5P / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / FAM180A / STK31 / MME / FAM180B / DACT3 / ADARB1 / SPN / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / MT1F / ITGBL1 / MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / RNU6-529P / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 / SYT15 / FAM155A / TMEM240 / VIT / ANKRD20A9P / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P / TENM3 / RFPL1S / LINC00937 / LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / CYP4F29P / ZNF883 / SNX18P13.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS GPR183									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T GPR183									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
NME9 - GPR183	320	335	331	173	PLAG1 - GPR183	344	260	248	1
BGN - GPR183	341	330	332	382	EPHB3 - GPR183	331	281	385	102
PLCB1 - GPR183	349	375	368	383	NTM - GPR183	388	367	348	299
RGS6 - GPR183	382	387	366	345	PAPPA - GPR183	387	358	380	233
PYCR1 - GPR183	346	268	276	108	NEB - GPR183	336	327	318	115
FAM43B - GPR183	311	326	295	198	TMEM119 - GPR183	370	369	386	209
OLFML1 - GPR183	330	344	350	188	DUSP5P1 - GPR183	324	363	365	234
ADRA2C - GPR183	352	311	376	189	PRKD1 - GPR183	390	377	367	300
CSF1 - GPR183	233	283	268	20	FLRT2 - GPR183	262	314	272	135
PRKG1 - GPR183	268	280	325	95	SHC4 - GPR183	375	319	347	182
CYP4Z1 - GPR183	329	350	222	391	CYP4X1 - GPR183	230	313	246	36
ANKRD20A5P - GPR183	391	372	381	363	C2orf88 - GPR183	278	323	342	132
KBTBD12 - GPR183	214	321	353	194	LDLRAD2 - GPR183	365	385	374	373
ENTPD8 - GPR183	367	324	317	235	PLAC9 - GPR183	371	308	356	346
NUGGC - GPR183	323	341	372	301	FAM180A - GPR183	369	391	354	302
STK31 - GPR183	242	234	282	111	MME - GPR183	345	386	370	347
FAM180B - GPR183	389	365	390	348	DACT3 - GPR183	310	292	330	112
ADARB1 - GPR183	220	322	306	231	SPN - GPR183	354	310	262	127
CLEC9A - GPR183	316	382	363	210	DLGAP2 - GPR183	339	366	379	349
MTIF - GPR183	289	354	321	184	ITGBL1 - GPR183	228	315	312	82
MMP17 - GPR183	353	374	351	350	DLL1 - GPR183	362	364	337	236
ZNF521 - GPR183	378	383	358	351	RYR3 - GPR183	372	380	338	381
RNU6-529P - GPR183	315	273	291	64	RHOT1P2 - GPR183	392	389	392	374
PLPP4 - GPR183	377	309	388	269	SYT15 - GPR183	319	318	287	352
FAM155A - GPR183	358	329	364	270	TMEM240 - GPR183	308	360	355	386
VIT - GPR183	384	388	377	303	ANKRD20A9P - GPR183	383	356	361	353
GPX3 - GPR183	373	347	369	237	HMGB3P7 - GPR183	359	362	333	364
ANKRD20A11P - GPR183	379	384	384	304	TENM3 - GPR183	376	392	389	305
RFPL1S - GPR183	244	339	244	78	LINC00937 - GPR183	356	288	284	72
LINC01907 - GPR183	338	303	300	53	ITGB2-AS1 - GPR183	364	361	339	238
LMCD1-AS1 - GPR183	313	316	207	142	CYP4F29P - GPR183	285	370	359	354
ZNF883 - GPR183	355	299	292	42	SNX18P13 - GPR183	381	368	371	355

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between GPR183 VS Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic GPR183 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of GPR183-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t GPR183	
CD38 / CD74 / RUNX3 / APBA2 / COL9A2 ...	
PDIA5 / FRY / ITGB5 / MMP2 / PCOLCE ...	
UNC5B / PMP22 / TRIM2 / TSPAN11 / VNN1 ...	
PARD3B / WLS / C1orf198 / PLXDC2 / PHF24 ...	
PLAU / FCHO1 / PTPN22 / LCP1 / TNS3 ...	
IL11RA / IGFBP4 / C1orf162 / TRIM7 ...	
ARID5B / KCNE4 / DDAH1 / SUSD3 / RUNX1 ...	
TCHH / MXRA8 / NLRP3 / TMEM71 / TVP23A ...	
NPNT / ATOH8 / ITGAM / GPR27 / MAP6 ...	
SCG2 / STARD5 / IL17D / SUSD5 / HOXB2 ...	
CD248 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / YPEL2 / FAM131A ...	
CABP4 / SLCO3A1 / BOK / MAMSTR / MYOZ1 ...	
PDE4DIP / CSRNP3 / CIITA / SERTM1 / KCNE1 ...	
NME9 / PLAG1 / BGN / EPHB3 / PLCB1 / NTM ...	
RGS6 / PAPP4 / PYCR1 / NEB / FAM43B / TMEM119 ...	
OLFML1 / DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C / PRKD1 / CSF1 ...	
FLRT2 / PRKG1 / SHC4 / CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 ...	
ANKRD20A5P / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 ...	
ENTPD8 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / FAM180A / STK31 ...	
MME / FAM180B / DACT3 / ADARB1 / SPN ...	
CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / MT1F / ITGBL1 / MMP17 ...	
DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / RNU6-529P / RHOT1P2 ...	
PLPP4 / SYT15 / FAM155A / TMEM240 / VIT ...	
ANKRD20A9P / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P ...	
TENM3 / RFPL1S / LINC00937 / LINC01907 ...	
ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / CYP4F29P / ZNF883 ...	
SNX18P13	GPR183

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between GPR183 and Individual members.

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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